

UNDERTREES: Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforEstry systems through a holistic methodological framework

UNDERTREES
AGROFORESTRY RESEARCH

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1. INTRODUCTION

The overarching objective of UNDERTREES is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of 15 organisations in 3 continents (Europe, Africa and South America) working on a joint research programme in the field of agroforestry (AF) and ecosystem services (ES) assessment. The participants are academic, government institutions and enterprises that will exchange skills and knowledge to progress towards key advances in agroforestry systems evaluation and design, while enhancing collaborative research and staff exchange across different continents. Skills and knowledge exchanges with African and South America countries, where agroforestry has a sound historical role in fostering environmental and socio-economical sustainability, will advance agroforestry systems comprehension, with significant benefits for the European environment and society. The staff members in the project will develop new skills, will be exposed to new research environments and will have their career perspectives widened. To achieve its aim, UNDERTREES identified research, training, and participatory activities at 16 study sites in 5 biogeographical areas, within three thematic areas: (1) agronomic and environmental sustainability, (2) socio-economic sustainability and (3) policy development. UNDERTREES will advance research by strengthening intersectoral cross-country collaboration, will provide training and education at academic and technical level, and will engage with local, national and international stakeholders to create shared knowledge on agroforestry ES for EU agricultural policy development.

Deliverable 5.1 presents an overview of the state of the art of network creation in the UNDERTREES countries (Italy, United Kingdom, Spain, Ghana, Ecuador and Chile) of three different continents (Europe, Africa and South America). All partners made a great effort to create networks in their countries, composed of different categories of actors (practitioners, private partners, multipliers, researchers, policy makers and administration) to guarantee a balanced composition from different perspectives and complementary types of knowledge. The core group of the UNDERTREES network is already created in all of the partner countries, but the composition can still evolve and new stakeholders will be included depending on the innovations, strategy, focus, expertise needed or interest of new practitioners.

Involved partners will try to involve at least one representative person for each category and to include a majority of 'practitioners' (farmers, foresters, land owners, etc) and farmer associations identified as 'multipliers' within the networks (a third of stakeholders is recommended). The total number of members in each network will be around 25, but it is currently composed of 6 to 100 stakeholders. At this moment, the UNDERTREES network has 171 members in total.

In deliverable 5.1 an overview is given of the actual composition of the networks (number and type of stakeholders), the focus of the networks, the method of contact with the stakeholders and the deviations or problems in the network creation.

2. NETWORK CREATION IN SPAIN

Focus of the network

Silvopastoral systems

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

In Galicia and Extremadura the agrarian economy is mainly oriented to livestock-based production systems (cattle dairy, beef, pigs, sheep and goat), so the stakeholder network will be mainly composed by livestock farmers that are already applying or willing to apply agroforestry (i.e. silvopastoral systems).

Number of participants

The Spanish network will have around 25-35 participants. Currently (end of January), we have 25 stakeholders (7 in Extremadura, central-western Spain and 18 in Galicia, NW Spain) that are very interested in participating and have signed the “letter of intent” and the “informed consent”. We have other people that have shown their interest but have not yet formalised their participation (by signing the letter of intent and the informed consent). At the moment, we would like to leave the network with a maximum of around 30 people because the stakeholders might find/decide that some new participants should be included (e.g. new multipliers or experts/researchers on a specific topic of their interest).

Category to which these belong (e.g. Farmers, scientists, others?)

In the case of the Spanish network, most of the stakeholders belong to the category ‘**multipliers**’ (around 36% of the total stakeholders) because some farmers work for farmer associations and chose to participate in the Spanish network on behalf of these farmer associations (identified as multipliers) instead of participating individually. It is important to be aware that the most representative farmer organisations from each livestock sector are represented in the Spanish network: e.g. sheep (OVICA, EA group), celtic autochthonous breeders (ASOPORCEL), Galician autochthonous breeders (BOAGA), Galician horse breeders (PURAGA),... The second largest category is ‘**practitioners**’ (mainly farmers, around 24% of the total stakeholders). Regarding the category of ‘**researchers**’, USC and UNEX researchers (already consortium partners) specialized in agroforestry systems will be part of the network. External researchers could be invited after identifying the range of topics that the stakeholders considered more interesting and feasible to be applied in the climatic conditions and the socio-economic context of the regions. On the other hand, some well-recognised ‘**private advisory services**’ (‘experts’) in both the agriculture and forestry sectors were also identified and invited to be part of the

network (Ambienta, Agroamb Prodalt S.L., Tragsatec...). Their expertise in the day-to-day practical management of both agricultural and forestry systems will be highly relevant when assessing the real applicability of the identified innovative agroforestry practices that can be implemented in the Spanish region. Finally, the '**public sector**'/'**administration**' is represented in the Spanish network by the Galician government through the Forest Districts, Provincial Council of Lugo and Agrarian Office of Lugo.

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders? Direct contact, letter, phone calls...

Stakeholders were contacted face-to-face (different farming events) and also by phone, after the first contact they were sent an email with the letter of intent and the informed consent to formalize their participation in the UNDERTREES network and also a short summary about the network (objectives, what the network offer to the participants and how the participants will contribute to the network).

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

No, the signed letters of intent and the informed consent are stored in the TEAMS platform of the UNDERTREES project.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

A survey to know the perception of the stakeholders about agroforestry will be circulated before the first network meeting.

3. NETWORK CREATION IN ITALY

Focus of the network

Development of agroforestry systems in Italy (silvopastoral and silvoarable)

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

The network will be composed by a variety of stakeholders involved in different type of agroforestry systems, such as silvopastoral, silvoarable, and agrosilvopastoral. All stakeholders work on agroforestry topics at a national level. Agroforestry is a possible alternative to conventional farming systems while providing ecosystem services. The overall idea of this network is to provide to policy makers scientifically sound data and good practices for implementing agroforestry systems to improve agricultural sustainability and resilience combine national (Rural Development Plans) and European level (CAP).

Number of participants

Initially, the Italian network will be composed by 6 participants. The six participants represent different actors of the Agroforestry system at the National level. The mentioned stakeholders have been involved in a Regional project during the last three years and will carry out different topics that have arisen during this period. We will include more participants depending on the topics of the meeting.

Category to which these belong (e.g. Farmers, scientists, others?)

The categories involved in the network include: Tenuta di Paganico farm (**farmer**) that is involved in different activities/experiments and initiatives on silvopastoral systems. AIAF (Italian agroforestry association), coordinates and promotes agroforestry topics and practices at the national level while interacting with other associations on an international level (**scientists**). CNR (National research council), will support the activities linked to environmental benefits provided by agroforestry systems (**scientists and technicians**). PEFC (Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification) will give its contribution to the inclusion of forest into agriculture and vice versa (**advisor and scientist**) and guarantee the quality of the system for possible certifications. University of Padova (**scientist, researcher**). NEWTON - EIP-AGRI Tuscany Region Operational Group, is a consortium that, as mentioned above, has worked on agroforestry topics on a regional level (**researchers and others**).

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders? Direct contact, letter, phone calls...

Stakeholders were contacted face-to-face or by phone and via email.

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

No, the signed letters of intent and the informed consent are stored in the TEAMS platform of the UNDERTREES project.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

A first activity has been planned for next December. The national agroforestry association (AIAF) forum will be organized in Rome, where we would like to present a poster about the Italian Undertrees network and the future planned activities within the project.

4. NETWORK CREATION IN THE UK (United Kingdom, comprising the four nations of England, Scotland, Wales (Great Britain) and Northern Ireland)

Focus of the network

The most representative agroforestry practices in our network is silvopasture, both in the lowland and uplands of the UK. The union of the UK comprises of the four nations of England, Scotland, Wales (together make up Great Britain) and Northern Ireland. Following 'Brexit' (UK exit from the EU - European Union) agricultural and forestry policy is devolved. This means it is made in the four nation capitals and not centrally, neither in Brussels and nor in London. The network covers the 4 nations and also is in close collaboration with the Republic of Ireland across the open border on this island. Besides Silvopasture there is limited silvoarable, silvohorticulture and home and urban gardens. There is also some forest farming (chicken, pig, cattle grazing inside farm woodland) and there is an extensive network of hedges and tall single trees across the two islands. A lot of traditional hedges (as field boundary, living fence for grazing) have been ripped out during the farm 'modernisation' drive in the 1960 and 1970, however this has completely stopped and is slowly reversed. All organic farms require hedges around the farm perimeter to avoid spray-drift from pesticides. There is also some riparian buffers and contour planting to avoid erosion as the high rainfall areas in the west of the country are also the more hilly or mountainous parts of the union. In the lowlands (East coast England and Scotland) large arable fields (too large >10 ha) dominate landscapes and here silvo-arable and reinstating smaller field sizes has enormous potential. Drought and wind erosion (sand storms) can be a severe problem on this exposed, dry and industrially farmed landscapes.

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

Although the uptake of agroforestry systems, either silvopasture or silvoarable, in the UK has been relatively low over the last 30 years, there is a good number of farmers across the four regions of the UK actively participating in its potential adoption within farming systems. Therefore, the stakeholder network will be mainly consisting of farmers and landowners who have taken part in government farming incentive schemes to establish agroforestry systems.

Number of participants

The UK network will consist of approx. 20 participants. Currently there are 15 stakeholders (England and Northern Ireland) that might be interested in participating. Through existing AFBI, Coventry University and the UK Farm Woodland Forum (<https://www.agroforestry.ac.uk>) networks, we have identified potential farmers who might be interested but not yet formalised their participation. With the

AGROMIX project and the Agroforestry Open days (<https://agroforestryopenweekend.org>) we are already well connected.

Category to which these belong (e.g. Farmers, scientists, others?)

In the UK, the definition of agroforestry is unclear with divergent approaches to integrating trees into the farming system across the four regions with different types of farming incentive schemes. Therefore stakeholders vary depending on the region and regulations within devolved administrations. Hence, in order to capture these differences, the network will be subdivided in land owners, policy makers and practitioners (researchers and professionals) from different devolved administrations in the UK.

Thus the network will examine the current status of agroforestry schemes and explore participation by undertaking survey work within the UK (mainly England and Northern Ireland) with stakeholders (questionnaires, interviews and focus groups; using existing event and cooperation with already well established networks), including **Farmers** who have already taken up agroforestry schemes, **Scientists** from AFBI and Coventry University and **Policy makers** from devolved administrations in England (DEFRA) and Northern Ireland (DAERA)

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders? Direct contact, letter, phone calls...

Stakeholders will be contacted either by email or phone, so they can confirm their participation. Subsequently a letter of intent and the informed consent will be formalised for their participation in the network, including a short summary about the network (objectives, what the network offer to the participants and how the participants will contribute to the network)

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

No, the signed letters of intent and the informed consent will be stored in the TEAMS platform of the UNDERTREES project.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

This phase of the work will draw on our survey work, the experiences of other UK regions in developing networks and lessons from other agricultural focus group networks. This will be informed

by our diagnosis of the actual causes of the difference in incentives between agroforestry systems in the UK.

5. NETWORK CREATION IN ECUADOR

Focus of the network

Agroforestry systems with cocoa, coffee and fruit trees

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

In the Ecuadorian Amazon, the production systems are oriented to traditional/conventional production systems, with the combination of trees, crops and animals. For this reason, it is important to strengthen the exchange of experiences in the management and conservation of these sustainable production systems. The network will initially be made up of cocoa, coffee and fruit producers who are linked to studies on agroforestry production systems.

Number of participants

Initially, the network in Ecuador will have 10 leaders of producer associations, who bring together more than 30 partners (indirect beneficiaries), located in the north and centre of the Ecuadorian Amazon. It has to be mentioned that the leaders are highly motivated to participate and have signed the "letter of intent" and the "informed consent". There are other people who have shown interest but have not yet formalized their participation (by signing the documents).

Category to which these belong

In the case of the Ecuadorian network, most of the interest groups belong to researchers (universities and technological institutes), multipliers (farmer associations) and practitioners (independent farmers are the 30% of the total stakeholders) who are facilitators of associative, productive and commercialization processes, because they have positions such as managers of the organizations or they are leading the academic sector. In this context, there are leaders of associations of cocoa, coffee, dragon fruit, and other fruit crops, and university professors who will contribute to the research processes.

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders?

Face-to-face meetings and telephone calls were held to inform about the objectives of the network. Later, an email was sent to them with the letter of intent and the informed consent thus they could analyze them within their organizations due to they represent a group of beneficiaries of their associations or institutions. In addition, they were informed about what the network offers to the participants and how they will contribute to it, especially in the training workshops.

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

No, the signed letters of intent and the informed consent are stored in the TEAMS platform of the UNDERTREES project.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

A survey to know the perception of the stakeholders about agroforestry will be circulated before the first network meeting.

6. NETWORK CREATION IN CHILE

Focus of the network

Silvopastoral systems

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

In Chile, most of the native forest is partly to highly degraded, mainly because of the presence of cattle, goats, and sheep for grazing. The National Forest Agency (CONAF) has no rules against such use, which keeps causing further degradation and destruction. As such, there is a need to establish sustainable silvopastoral systems to control its use and allow small farmers to continue using the forests within their property and around, without destroying it and contaminating water courses. Additionally, this practice will help CONAF to achieve its international commitment towards the restoration and provision of ecosystem services.

Number of participants

The Chilean network will have around 25 participants. Currently (early February), we have 15 stakeholders (located in the surroundings of the Ranchillo Alto state-owned property, Yungay Commune, Ñuble Region, south central Chile) who have actively participated in the implementation of a 30-ha silvopastoral system and used it for their animals up to now. They keep very interested to continue using it and establish a similar system within their property. A few years ago, they have signed a “letter of intent” and an “informed consent” which will be signed again under the framework of the UNDERTREES project. At the moment, we would like to leave the network with a maximum of 35 stakeholders in order to assure its control and its expansion across the country, especially in biomes with different vegetation, climate and topography.

Category to which these belong (e.g., Farmers, scientists, others?)

In the case of the Chilean network, all the stakeholders belong to the category of practitioners (small farmers), whose properties are less than 5 ha. The Chilean Forest Institute (INFOR) established several years ago a small agroforestry program to help and motivate people to adopt such systems, to provide basic resources for their implementation, and to monitor them over the years. Regarding the category of researchers, UdeC and PUC researchers (already partners of UNDERTREES) who are all specialized in agroforestry will be part of the network. More researchers will be invited after identifying the range of topics that the stakeholders considered more interesting and feasible to be applied in different climatic and topographical conditions, taking in consideration the socio-economic context of the regions.

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders? Direct contact, letter, phone calls...

Stakeholders were contacted face-to-face for the first time between 2014-2018. They were then given the letter of intent and the informed consent to formalize their participation in the network and a detailed summary about the overall project.

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

No problems at all, nor special remarks now.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

A survey to know the perception of the stakeholders about agro-silviculture and silvopastoralism will be produced before the first network meeting.

7. NETWORK CREATION IN GHANA

Focus of the network

Agroforestry systems (Agri-silviculture, Silvopastoral and Agri-silvo-pastoral), Cottage “Circular Economy” concept

Motivate briefly why and how this focus was chosen

Due to land hunger, some farmers resort to employing agroforestry systems to be able to make maximum use of the parcel of land they possess. Ghana possesses various degrees of wet and dry ecological zones so the network will embrace farmers from both zones. These farmers practice either of the 3 main agroforestry systems.

In the Savannah (dry) zone, some research work was carried out on farmer fields in 8 communities, in Talensi Nabdam and Kassena Nankana districts within the Guinea Savannah ecological zone whilst Garu-Tempene and Bawku Municipality fall within the Sudan Savannah zone, all in the Upper West Region of Ghana. In this region, almost every household keep livestock so almost all farmers practice agro-silvo-pastoral.

In the moist and wet zone, at one site, Dawu Sanfo in the Eastern Region of Ghana the farmer is into cocoa agroforestry. However, farmers from 4 communities under Juaben Municipality and 6 communities under Effiduase Municipality, all in Ashanti of Ghana, 52.5 % are into Silvopastoral while 47.5 % are into Agri-silvo-pastoral.

The Cottage “Circular Economy” Concept is an integrated farming system that specializes in sustainable agricultural systems that combines aquaculture, crop production, livestock and other non-traditional farming units. It features the Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) for aquaculture production, aquaponics, poultry, non-traditional farming, vegetable production and livestock. The Cottage employs the circular economy model, where waste is continuously recycled and reused in an environmentally friendly manner.

Number of participants

The agroforestry network will have about 100-120 participants made up of farmers and researchers. Some have just been contacted face-to-face and some on phone and they have shown their interest. Others are yet to be contacted and hopefully, they will agree to join the network. Interested participants will then be made to sign their “letters of intent” and the “informed consent” for the formalisation of their participation.

The Cottage also doubles as a training centre and has successfully built the capacity of over 1200 farmers in the area of integrated aquaculture-crop production system since 2016. Currently, there are over 350 RAS fishponds installed by about 90 clients across the country and still counting.

Category to which these belong (e.g. Farmers, scientists, others?)

In the case of the Ghana network, most of the stakeholders are practitioners (farmers), though, some are care-taker farmers. Concerning the category of '**researchers**', Scientists from CSIR-Forestry Research Institute of Ghana and CSIR-Crops Research Institute will be part of the network. External researchers may be invited as and when stakeholders identify certain pertinent or interesting issues.

At least 50 people including students visit the Cottage on weekly basis to learn about aquaculture especially the business model of RAS ponds.

How did you decide to contact the stakeholders? Direct contact, letter, phone calls...

The network emanated from different projects that were undertaken. In these projects, there are community entries where the stakeholders are contacted. Those who expressed interest were engaged. Circulars were also sent around for workshops that were organized and those who showed interest applied either through emails, letters or phone calls.

Are there problems or remarks concerning the network creation (if so, describe)

In the past, when previous networks were created, interests waned when projects supporting some of the activities ended. However, projects that had bailout plans for sustainability in terms of revenue generation continued.

Any deviations in the planning? (if so, describe)

Deviations were not identified.

Anything else? surveys, letter, leaflets produced to aid the network creation

The UNDERTREES network is based on a network created from previous projects.